

A Study of Relationship of Smartphone Addiction and Social Motives of Students Studying at Senior Secondary Level

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Abstract

The objective of the present study is to measure the relationship of Smartphone Addiction and Social Motives of senior secondary level students. This is a survey study under descriptive research. For the present study, the population was all the male and female students of J.V. Jain Inter College, Saharanpur, Uttar Pradesh. 100 students were selected as the samples. For the collection of data the researcher administrated the Smartphone Addiction Scale by Vijayshri and Dr. Masaud Ansari, and Social Motives Scale by Dr. Ram Nayan Singh and Dr. Mahesh Bhargava. After that, data of Smartphone Addiction and Social Motives scores were calculated and relationship between them was sought with Pearson's Product Moment Correlation and the results were analyzed & interpretations were drawn. The levels of significance were kept 0.01 and 0.05 to test the hypotheses. It was observed from the findings of the variables that there is no significant relationship exists between them.

Key words : Smartphone, Addiction, Social, Motives, Senior Secondary

Introduction

At present, Smartphone become a crucial part of our daily lifestyles, even our personal as well as professional activities totally influence by it. Either elders or children everyone uses smartphone. Due to excess use of smartphone leads to its addiction. A lot of content on different websites such as gaming platforms affect the behaviour of individuals and as well as their social motives.

Smartphone Addiction is a disorder involving compulsive overuse of the mobile devices, usually quantified as the number of times user access their devices or the total amount of time they are online over a specified period.

Social Motives are the psychological processes that drive people's thinking, feeling and behaviour in interactions with other people. Motives implied in social events or behaviours are called social motives. When any person responds to another person or social signs and symbols, then his behaviour is termed as social behaviour.

Literature Review

Taseen Islam (2020), in his study found that the impact of smart phone technology has harmful impacts on both the quantity and quality of face to face communication and human behaviour and relationship. Sheopuri and Sheopuri (2014) observed that extent of addictive behavior towards the usage of smart phones and the relation between the users of the smart phone and the psychological behavior among adolescents in Bhopal, India. They showed that smart phone usage is so strongly integrated into young people's behavior that symptoms of behavior addiction, such as smart phone usage interrupting their day to day activities. Whitbourn (2011), smartphone are making people less smart. There have been concerns about the negative impact smart phone have on human intelligence, with regards to memory

(Sparrow, Liu & Wegner 2011), spatial orientation (Bohbat et. al. 2011) and higher level cognitive tasks (Abraham et v.al 2009). It influences the development of social structures and how users perceive themselves and the world around them and it is now customary that a ringing or beeping phone takes priority over the social interactions it disrupts (Plant 2001).

Significance of the study

This study provided an insight to the recognized reliance on the use of smartphone in this day & age. The findings of the study are beneficial because most of the individuals do not realize how much smartphone addiction hinders their social motives, even in the minor way. This study enhances the understanding on the relationship of smartphone addiction and social motives of students.

Statement of Problem : "A study of Relationship of Smartphone Addiction and Social Motives of Students Studying at Senior Secondary Level".

Delimitation of the study :

- 1- The present study has been limited to the students at studying senior of Uttar Pradesh Board of Education.
- 2- The present study has not been reached to the every age group that use smartphone.
- 3- This study has been confined to students of J.V. Jain Inter College, Saharanpur, Uttar Pradesh.

Objectives :

- 1- To study the relationship between Smartphone Addiction and Social Motives of student studying at senior secondary level.
- 2- To Study the relationship between Compulsion and Social Motives of students studying at senior secondary level.
- 3- To study the relationship between Forgetfulness and Social Motives of students studying at senior secondary level.
- 4- To study the relationship between Lack of Attention and Social Motives of students studying at senior secondary level.
- 5- To study the relationship between Depression/Anxiety and Social Motives of students studying at senior secondary level.
- 6- To study the relationship between Disturbed hunger/ sleep and Social Motive of students studying at senior secondary level.
- 7- To study the relationship between Social Withdrawal and Social Motives of students studying at senior secondary level.

Hypotheses :

- 1- There is no significant relationship between Smartphone Addiction and Social Motives of is students studying at senior secondary level.
- 2- There is no significant relationship between Compulsion and Social Motives of students studying at senior secondary level.
- 3- There is no significant relationship between Forgetfulness and Social Motives of students studying at senior secondary level.
- 4- There is no significant relationship between Lack of Attention and Social Motives of students studying at senior secondary level.
- 5- There is no significant relationship between Depression/Anxiety and Social Motives of students studying at senior secondary level.
- 6- There is no significant relationship between Disturbed Hunger/Sleep and Social Motives of students studying at senior secondary level.
- 7- There is no significant relationship between Social Withdrawal and Social Motives of students studying at senior secondary level.

Methodology :

- ❖ **Research Design-** The Descriptive Survey Research Method has been applied in the study.
- ❖ **Population, Sample, Age Limit of Sample-** The present study consisted 100 students (50 males & 50 females) of senior secondary level of J.V. Jain Inter College, Saharanpur, of age group 15 to 19 years old.
- ❖ **Variables-**
Independent Variables - Smartphone Addiction
Dependent Variables - Social Motives
- ❖ **Tools-** To measure Smartphone Addiction, Smartphone Addiction Scale constructed by Dr. Vijayshri & Dr. Masaud Ansari has been used. This tool has six dimensions namely Compulsion, Forgetfulness, Lack of Attention, Depression/Anxiety, Distributed Hunger/Sleep and Social Withdrawal.
To measure Social Motives, Social Motives Scale constructed by Dr. Ram Nayan Singh & Dr. Mahesh Bhargava has been used.
- ❖ **Statistical Techniques-** Product Moment Correlation has been used to measure the relationship between of both the variables, Smartphone Addiction and Social Motives.

Data Analysis & Interpretation

To test the relationship between the variables of the study Pearson's Product Moment correlation technique was applied. Significance of correlation coefficient was checked afterwards to test the significance of the hypotheses.

The results obtained are mentioned in the given table:

S.No.	Relationship Between	'r' value	Level of significance
1	Smartphone Addiction & Social Motives	0.148	Not Significant
2	Compulsion & Social Motives	0.1089	Not Significant
3	Forgetfulness & Social Motives	0.075	Not Significant
4	Lack of Attention & Social Motives	0.1998	Significant only at 0.05 level
5	Depression/Anxiety & Social Motives	0.213	Significant only at 0.05 level
6	Distributed Hunger/Sleep & Social Motives	0.094	Not Significant
7	Social Withdrawal & Social Motives	0.0806	Not Significant

Interpretation for Hypothesis 1: Obtained value of 'r' for hypothesis is 0.148. Thus there is positive but negligible relationship between both variables. The magnitude of 'r' is very low. While considering the critical value of 'r', at 0.05 & 0.01 level (0.195 & 0.254 respectively), it is found that r value is not significant at both the levels of confidence hence it may be interpreted that no significant relationship exist between Smartphone Addiction & Social Motives of students studying at senior secondary level. Thus null hypothesis is accepted.

Interpretation for Hypothesis 2: Obtained value of 'r' for hypothesis is 0.1089. Thus there is positive but negligible relationship between both the variables. The magnitude of 'r' is very low. While considering the critical value of 'r', at 0.05 & 0.01 level (0.195 & 0.254 respectively), it is found that r value is not significant at both the levels of confidence hence it may be interpreted that no significant relationship exist between Compulsion & Social Motives of students studying at senior secondary level. Thus null hypothesis is accepted.

Interpretation for Hypothesis 3: Obtained value of 'r' for hypothesis is 0.075. Thus there is positive but negligible relationship between both the variables. The magnitude of 'r' is very low. While considering the critical value of 'r', at 0.05 & 0.01 level (0.195 & 0.254 respectively), it is found that r value is not significant at both the levels of confidence hence it may be interpreted that no significant relationship exist between Forgetfulness & Social Motives of students studying at senior secondary level. Thus null hypothesis is accepted.

Interpretation for Hypothesis 4: Obtained value of 'r' for hypothesis is 0.1998. Thus there is positive but low level of relationship between both the variables. The magnitude of 'r' is low. While considering the critical value of 'r', at 0.05 & 0.01 level (0.195 & 0.254 respectively), it is found that r value is not significant at 0.01 level but significant at 0.05 level of confidence hence it may be interpreted that there is partially significant relationship exist between Lack of Attention & Social Motives of students studying at senior secondary level. Thus null hypothesis is partially rejected.

Interpretation for Hypothesis 5: Obtained value of 'r' for hypothesis is 0.213. Thus there is positive but low level of relationship between both the variables. The magnitude of 'r' is low. While considering the critical value of 'r', at 0.05 & 0.01 level (0.195 & 0.254 respectively), it is found that r value is not significant at 0.01 level but significant at 0.05 level of confidence hence it may be interpreted that there is partially significant relationship exist between Depression/Anxiety & Social Motives of students studying at senior secondary level. Thus null hypothesis is partially rejected.

Interpretation for Hypothesis 6: Obtained value of 'r' for hypothesis is 0.094. Thus there is positive but negligible relationship between both the variables. The magnitude of 'r' is very low. While considering the critical value of 'r', at 0.05 & 0.01 level (0.195 & 0.254 respectively), it is found that r value is not significant at both the levels of confidence hence it may be interpreted that no significant relationship exist between Distributed Hunger/Sleep & Social Motives of students studying at senior secondary level. Thus null hypothesis is accepted.

Interpretation for Hypothesis 7: Obtained value of 'r' for hypothesis is 0.0806. Thus there is positive but negligible relationship between both the variables. The magnitude of 'r' is very low. While considering the critical value of 'r', at 0.05 & 0.01 level (0.195 & 0.254 respectively), it is found that r value is not significant at both the levels of confidence hence it may be interpreted that no significant relationship exist between Social Withdrawal & Social Motives of students studying at senior secondary level. Thus null hypothesis is accepted.

Conclusion

This study finds the relationship between Smartphone Addiction and Social Motives based upon the correlation coefficients presented through the table. On the basis of findings of the study it may be concluded that the Smartphone Addiction along with its dimensions has positive correlation with Social Motives, although the magnitude of relationship is very low or almost negligible. The findings are in support of the notion that there is low level of Smartphone Addiction will lead low Social Motives.

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